

Carbon export in an Arctic frontal system in Fram Strait

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ABSTRACT

Recent studies report high carbon export efficiencies in Arctic regions with seasonal sea ice compared to ice-free regions, yet the mechanisms behind this enhanced export remain unclear. In the marginal ice zone (MIZ), where pack ice meets open ocean, eddies and filaments frequently form. To investigate carbon export mechanisms in such frontal systems, we combined direct *in situ* observations of export processes and physical oceanography using free-drifting sediment traps, Marine Snow Catchers, and *in situ* optics during a Fram Strait expedition in July 2020. Dense Atlantic Water (AW) subducted beneath lighter surface meltwater and Polar Water (PW), structuring biogeochemical and biological processes, including chlorophyll distribution, primary production, zooplankton abundance, microbial respiration, and aggregate formation. We observed three main mechanisms supporting carbon export; (i) deep aggregate formation driven by the subduction of chlorophyll-rich AW, (ii) diatom ballasting of aggregates, including slow-sinking *Phaeocystis* colonies, and (iii) cryogenic mineral ballasting in PW aggregates, which increased sinking velocities up to tenfold. High carbon fluxes occurred in the AW and at the front, while export in PW was lower, highlighting the role of water mass characteristics and ballasting in regulating export efficiency. The results suggest that continued Atlantification and expansion of the MIZ could enhance carbon export across larger Arctic areas as sea ice retreats.

1. Introduction

The Arctic is strongly subjected to anthropogenic climate change and is warming faster than anywhere else on Earth (e.g. Serreze and Francis, 2006; England et al., 2021; Rantanen et al., 2022), which impacts the Arctic ecosystems, biogeochemistry, carbon export, and carbon sequestration. Sea ice extent is declining under climate change (Parkinson and DiGirolamo, 2021), which is affecting all connected biological processes. It has been shown that there is an increasing carbon flux with decreasing distance to sea ice, suggesting that in Arctic regions with seasonal sea ice cover, carbon export is higher compared to ice-free regions (Fadeev et al., 2021a). The export efficiency in ice-covered regions is very high, especially during export event such as release and

sedimentation of ice-algae (Arrigo et al., 2012; Boetius et al., 2013). Thinning of sea ice and increased light penetration has been suggested to enhance primary production and ice-algae carbon export (Arrigo et al., 2012; Boetius et al., 2013), at least in the short term until sea ice algae will disappear with the loss of sea ice in the Arctic. Nevertheless, enhanced water column stratification due to sea ice melt and input of meltwater seems to delay and decrease carbon export via the biological carbon pump (von Appen et al., 2021).

On the other hand, increasing warming and intrusion of Atlantic Water (AW) to the Arctic may lead to a shift in seasonal zooplankton distribution and a community change towards Atlantic species (Neukermans et al., 2018; Ramondenc et al., 2023), as it is already observed with increasing occurrence of the Atlantic haptophyte

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Phaeocystis (Nöthig et al., 2015). Less carbon is exported in *Phaeocystis*-dominated regions, with smaller aggregates compared to ice-covered, diatom-dominated regions (Fadeev et al., 2021a). Slower sinking velocities of the non-ballasted *Phaeocystis* aggregates allow more time for microbial degradation and remineralization at shallow depths compared to faster settling diatom-dominated aggregates, weakening pelagic-benthic coupling and export efficiency (Fadeev et al., 2021a; Ramondenc et al., 2025; Reigstad and Wassmann, 2007). Thus, it is crucial to understand how future sea ice conditions will impact the Arctic ecosystem and carbon sequestration.

The marginal ice zone (MIZ), i.e. the region where sea ice meets the open ocean and the surface ocean is impacted by meltwater, is narrowing during the cold season, while it is widening in the warm season (Strong and Rigor, 2013). During the past decades, the MIZ experienced a 39% widening in summer (Strong and Rigor, 2013). In the MIZ in Fram Strait, especially in areas with ice concentration below 20%, sub-mesoscale or mesoscale eddies occur frequently (Kozlov and Atadzhanova, 2021). In this region, denser and warmer AW is subducted below the lighter and fresher Polar Water (PW), which is possibly connected to eddy processes (Hattermann et al., 2016). These subduction processes can transport organic material, including slow-sinking and suspended particles to depth and enhance the carbon export and export efficiency (Boyd et al., 2019; Omand et al., 2015; Rogge et al., 2022). Additionally, the vertical mixing in Fram Strait can also resupply nutrients and enhance primary production (Mahadevan, 2016; Tippenhauer et al., 2021).

Submesoscale or mesoscale eddies can result in the formation of frontal filaments. One of such submesoscale Arctic frontal filaments was first investigated in summer 2017 (Fadeev et al., 2021b; von Appen et al., 2018). The filament was characterized by density anomalies down to 400 m depth, pointing towards possible deep effects of the front on biological processes (von Appen et al., 2018). The submesoscale mixing process resulted in high primary productivity and carbon export (Fadeev et al., 2021b). Within just a few kilometers distance, the microbial community and the observed biogeochemistry varied in the different

water masses (Fadeev et al., 2021b). Due to limited time spent at the frontal filament, the processes responsible for the carbon export were not fully determined in the study and the effect of meltwater and ice coverage was not quantified.

To address these largely uninvestigated processes, we targeted a frontal system in the MIZ in Fram Strait. The aim was to assess the carbon export, export mechanisms, and export efficiency in the front and their relation to the physical oceanographic processes (e.g., advection and subduction). Water masses showed differences in biological characteristics, e.g. phytoplankton concentration, zooplankton abundances, microbial respiration, carbon export, the abundance of aggregates, and aggregate characteristics. Using free-drifting sediment traps, Marine Snow Catchers (MSCs), *in situ* optics, and water mass properties, we identified the dominant export mechanisms in the frontal zone.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Sampling region and physical oceanographic conditions

In Fram Strait, warm and salty Atlantic Water (AW) in the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC) is flowing northward (Aagaard et al., 1987; Beszczynska-Möller et al., 2012), while cold and fresher Polar Water (PW) in the East Greenland Current (EGC) is flowing southward (Håvik et al., 2017). The two water masses meet in the central Fram Strait, mostly due to recirculating AW (Hofmann et al., 2021). This results in the development of density fronts between PW and AW in the marginal ice zone (MIZ). During the cruise MSM93 onboard RV *Maria S. Merian* in July 2020, a front system at the ice edge in the MIZ in Fram Strait was targeted (Fig. 1 A). The surface meltwater was characterized by temperatures between 0.5 °C and 2 °C and salinities of <33.3 (Hofmann et al., 2024). The PW had temperatures between -2 °C and 0 °C and salinities between 33.7 and 34.4 and the AW had temperatures between 3 °C and 5 °C and salinities >34.5 (Hofmann et al., 2024).

In situ camera systems to detect particles and aggregates were deployed together with a CTD at all 29 stations (Fig. 1 B), including a 36

Fig. 1. (A) Map with study region (orange square) showing the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC, red) and the East Greenland Current (EGC, blue), (B) map of sampling stations of *in situ* camera, Marine Snow Catcher, and drifting traps, with shadings showing bathymetry, and (C) surface daily mean chlorophyll *a* (Chla) distribution [mg m^{-3}] based on Aqua MODIS in the environs of the camera transect (Stations 30-39). The drifting trap and MSC stations were in three different water masses; Atlantic Water (AW: station 51/56), in the frontal system (station 88), and in Polar Water (PW: station 99).

km long *in situ* camera transect (stations 30 – 39, 7th of July 2020; Fig. 1 C), to investigate particle and aggregate dynamics in the frontal system in relation to the water mass velocity fields (vessel-mounted Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) data), satellite data, and the physical oceanographic conditions described by Hofmann et al. (2024). Data processing for the vessel-mounted ADCP (75 kHz Teledyne RDI) is described by Hofmann et al. (2024). To get an overview of the distribution of the chlorophyll-rich water masses in the camera transect, chlorophyll *a* (Chla) concentrations were extracted from the daily mean Chla data set (Hu et al., 2012) based on the Aqua MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer sensor, available at <https://oc.eandata.sci.gsfc.nasa.gov>) satellite data. The data had a 4 km spatial resolution and was recorded on the 6th of July 2020, one day prior to sampling, as no data was available on the 7th due to cloud coverage.

2.2. Vertical distributions and morphology of *in situ* particles and aggregates

Vertical profiles of particle and aggregate size-distribution and abundance (i.e. aggregate profiles) were recorded with *in situ* camera systems. These consisted of an Underwater Vision Profiler UVP5 (Picheral et al., 2010) and a “remotely observing *in situ* camera for aggregates” system (ROSINA), which were mounted together on one frame and were lowered with a speed of 0.3 m s⁻¹. The UVP was used to determine zooplankton abundances in the camera transect. The ROSINA system was used for the determination of particle and aggregate abundances and properties in the water column. The ROSINA camera system includes a 29 MPixel camera (SVS-Vistek) and a Canon EF 60 mm f/2.8 Macro USM lens with an image acquisition rate of 2 pictures per second. The light source was a custom-made background light source with a reflective light source (Falcon Illumination, Kronmeyer LED Driver). A CTD (Itronaut OceanSeven 310) with optical oxygen sensor, Seapoint Turbidity Meter, and a Seapoint Chlorophyll Fluorometer was attached to the camera system. At some stations, the implemented CTD had a system failure and we used the pressure sensor of the UVP for depth calibration and data from rosette CTD for the environmental conditions, when available.

The field of view of the ROSINA camera system was 64.116 mm wide and 42.744 mm high (Length x Width, 6576 x 4384 Pixels) with a depth of field of 30 mm resulting in a sampling volume of 82.2 mL per captured image. The pixel size in the acquired images of the ROSINA camera system was 9.75 $\mu\text{m pixel}^{-1}$. The images were processed with an OpenCV image processing software. A reference image was generated for each downcast by averaging the grayscale intensity values of all images, producing a mean intensity for every pixel on the image sensor. Because *in situ* particles and aggregates are relatively rare, this averaged image represents the background light field without particles, essentially a blank background image. The resulting background image from each deployment was then used to correct individual images by subtracting image artefacts such as uneven illumination, vignetting near the edges, and irregularities on the sensor, lens, or backlight. After background subtraction and image inversion, the final processed images displayed particles and aggregates as bright objects against a dark background. A threshold binary was set to be 1.3-fold above the average background pixel grey value. Subsequent erosion and dilation were used on the images to remove noise. The program searched for particle contours (minimum particle size = 5 pixel) and determined the particle and aggregate parameters. The image parameters were calculated according to Trudnowska et al. (2021), including particle and aggregate area, equivalent spherical diameter (ESD), volume, circularity, elongation, and mean grey value (Table S1 in the supplementary information). Zooplankton images of the UVP were sorted using the EcoTaxa web application (Picheral et al., 2017) in larger taxonomic groups such as copepoda, ostracoda, chaetognatha, amphipoda, mollusca, annelida, cnidaria, detritus, and fibers.

2.3. Definition of particles and aggregates

In this study, we distinguish between particles and aggregates by considering that the term particles refer to any discrete pieces of material in the water column, including biological matter (e.g., phytoplankton cells, detritus, bacteria), mineral fragments, or zooplankton fecal pellets, spanning a wide size range from submicron to centimeter scales. The term is generic and does not imply any particular formation process. In contrast, aggregates are composite structures formed by the adhesion or coagulation of multiple smaller particles through physical collisions, biological sticking agents (e.g., transparent exopolymer particles, TEP), or biological packaging (e.g. zooplankton fecal pellets or feeding structures, such as pteropod feeding nets and appendicularian houses). When these aggregates have a diameter larger than 500 μm , we refer to them as marine snow. Aggregates are typically porous, heterogeneous in composition, possess emergent properties such as increased size, altered density, and enhanced sinking velocities compared to their constituent particles. While fecal pellets can exist as individual particles, they may also be fragmented or incorporated into larger aggregates, thereby contributing to the formation and dynamics of marine snow. The distinction between aggregate types were done microscopically for each individual aggregate collected with the Marine Snow Catcher and via sorting of the cropped individual aggregates collected in the gel traps and captured by the *in situ* camera systems.

2.4. Biogeochemistry

To determine the biogeochemical export flux, we collected settling aggregates with an array of free-drifting surface-tethered sediment traps. The sediment traps were deployed three times, targeting the AW, the PW, and the front. The free-drifting sediment traps were deployed for a duration of between 12 h and 21 h and were equipped with a surface buoy, 18 buoyancy spheres serving as wave-breakers, two 25 L buoyancy spheres, and a positioning system. Three sediment trap stations were vertically deployed at 100 m, 200 m, and 400 m depth, respectively, with four collection tubes at each collection depth. Filtered seawater was added in the collection tubes prior to the deployment with additional NaCl to increase the salinity by about 3 PSU. One trap tube per depth contained a gel trap with an ethanol-based viscous cryo-gel (Tissue-Tek, O.C.T.TM COMPOUND, Sakura) that preserved the structure, shape, and size of the fragile settling particles and aggregates for microscopic analysis. The remaining three trap tubes at each sediment trap station depth collected the sinking material that was used for subsequent biogeochemical analyses. One of these trap tubes was fixed with HgCl₂ and used for bulk biogeochemical analyses. The remaining two trap tubes were frozen at -20 °C and stored for future analyses.

After recovery of the sediment traps, we placed the traps in the dark and allowed the settling material to sediment at the bottom of the trap tubes before we siphoned the overlaying water out of the tube and only collected settled material for analyzes of total particulate mass (TPM), particulate organic carbon (POC), particulate organic nitrogen (PON), particulate inorganic carbon (PIC), and biogenic silica (bSi). For POC, PON, and PIC measurements, material was filtered onto two individual pre-weighted GF/F filters (Whatman, 25 mm), one for POC and PON and one for PIC and PON, the filters were dried at 50 °C for 24 h and re-weighed to determine the TPM. For POC measurements, the filters were fumed with 37% HCl for 24 h and dried again at 50 °C for 24 h, while the filters used for PIC were not fumed with 37% HCl and, therefore, contained both PIC and POC. The filters were analyzed using a GC elemental analyser (EuroEA Elemental Analyser, HEKAtech). The PIC content was calculated by subtracting the carbon measured on the fumed filter (i.e. the GF/F filter prepared for POC and PON) from the non-fumed filter (i.e. the GF/F filter prepared for PIC). For bSi, the material from the collection tubes was filtered onto cellulose acetate 0.8 μm filters (Sartorius, 25 mm), dried, processed by wet-alkaline digestion and spectrometrically determined (Bodungen et al., 1991). All

biogeochemical measurements were normalized by the opening area of the trap tube and deployment time of the sediment trap.

Lithogenic fluxes were calculated with the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{lithogenic fluxes [mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}] &= \text{TPM} - \text{CaCO}_3 - \text{SiO}_2 - 2 \text{ POC} \\ &= \text{TPM} - \frac{60}{28} \text{ bSi} - \frac{100}{12} \text{ PIC} - 2 \text{ POC} \end{aligned}$$

2.5. Water sampling for nutrients, microscopic plankton community assessments and primary production

A CTD (SBE11plus, Sea-Bird Scientific) was deployed to measure temperature, salinity, chlorophyll *a* fluorescence, turbidity, and dissolved oxygen. On the CTD rosette, 24 Niskin bottles, each with a volume of 10 L, were mounted to collect water samples for nutrient analysis at six to eight different water depths. Ammonium concentrations were measured on board with the standard fluorometric method (Holmes et al., 1999). 50 mL water samples were frozen at -20°C for nutrient analysis and measured in the home laboratory (Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Bremerhaven, Germany). The nutrients (nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, silicate) were analyzed using a QuAAtro Seal Analytical Continuous Segmented Flow Autoanalysers following colorimetric techniques (Aminot and Kerouel, 2007; Aminot et al., 2009; Grasshoff et al., 2009; Kirkwood, 1996) and GO-SHIP best practices (Becker et al., 2020; Hydes et al., 2010).

Additionally, a microscopic assessment of phytoplankton and microzooplankton was done onboard. For this, 50 mL water samples were taken from the Chl_a maximum depth, fixed with formaldehyde to a final concentration of 2% and settled in an Utermhl chamber for 12 h before the phytoplankton and microzooplankton was analyzed semi-quantitatively using an inverse light microscope (Axiovert 25, Zeiss Inverse Microscope).

Primary production was measured at each free-drifting sediment trap deployment. To do this, we collected water from 10 m, 25 m, 50 m, and 75 m using the CTD-Rosette and incubated 1 - 1.2 L in filled airtight PE bottles. To determine the start POC concentration and the carbon isotope ratio of carbon-13 and carbon-12 in the phytoplankton, 1 - 2 L of seawater was filtered onto pre-combusted GF/F filters (Whatman, 25 mm) immediately after sampling. One light and one dark bottle was labeled with stable carbon-13 isotopes ($\text{NaH}^{13}\text{CO}_3$) for each depth, attached to the drifting traps at the corresponding depths and were incubated during the deployment of the free-drifting trap array. Dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) samples were taken from each of the bottles prepared for primary production and fixed with HgCl_2 and stored in Exetainer® vials (Labco, 12 mL) to measure the labeling concentration, before deployment and after recovery. The DIC samples were analyzed on a Picarro G2101-i equipped with a custom-built purge system for total DIC measurements in the home laboratory. After recovery, the remaining bottle content was filtered onto GF/F filters (Whatman, 25 mm) for POC analysis and carbon-13 and carbon-12 isotope ratio. The filters were dried at 50°C for 24 h, fumed with 37% HCl for 24 h and dried again at 50°C for 24 h. A quarter of each fumigated and dried filter was measured with a combustion module attached to a cavity ring-down spectroscopy analyser (CM-CRDS, with a Picarro G2101-i Analyzer).

The gross specific primary production rate (μ_{POC} , d^{-1}) was derived from the Mass-Ratio Progress model for DMSP production (Stefels et al., 2009):

$$\mu_{\text{POC}} = \frac{\ln \left(\frac{\%^{13}\text{C DIC} - \%^{13}\text{C POC}_{\text{start}}}{\%^{13}\text{C DIC} - \%^{13}\text{C POC}_{\text{end}}} \right)}{t}$$

using the label ratio of ^{13}C in the dissolved inorganic carbon in the incubation ($\%^{13}\text{C DIC}$), the ratio of ^{13}C in the POC at the start of the incubation ($\%^{13}\text{C POC}_{\text{start}}$), the ratio of ^{13}C in the POC at the end of the incubation ($\%^{13}\text{C POC}_{\text{end}}$), and time (t , d). Then, the primary production

(PP , $\text{mgC m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$) in the incubations was calculated by multiplying the POC concentration (POC_{conc} , mgC m^{-3}) in the water by the gross specific growth rate (μ_{POC} , d^{-1}).

To calculate the total primary production in the euphotic zone, we used depth profiles of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), since there was no clear mixed layer in the frontal system. The PAR profiles were obtained from the integral over depth resolved hyperspectral downwelling irradiance spectra measured by a radiometer (RAMSES ACC-2-VIS, TriOS GmbH, Germany) covering a wavelength range of 320 nm to 950 nm with an optical resolution of 3.3 nm and a spectral accuracy of 0.3 nm installed on a light profiler and lowered until 100 m at CTD stations (Bracher et al., 2020). We fitted a logarithmic function through the measured primary production rate ($\text{mgC m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$) as a function of the percentage of PAR at the corresponding depth [%] and used this function to calculate the primary production stepwise in 5 m steps between 5 m and 70 m. We summed the calculated step-wise primary production to get the total primary production of the photic zone ($\text{mgC m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$).

2.6. Sinking velocities and respiration

While the free-drifting sediment traps collected either a pool of settling particles and aggregates for biogeochemical analyses, or individual, intact aggregates embedded in the gel traps for determination of their type, size, and abundance, we also used a Marine Snow Catcher (MSC) to collect individual, intact, and non-embedded aggregates for direct laboratory measurements. The MSC is a hundred liter water sampler that was lowered to the depth approximately 10 m below the Chl_a maximum in the AW, the PW, and the front. Here we used a drop weight (messenger) to activate the releaser that closed the MSC and allowed us to bring a 100 L core of the water column back to the ship, including all the settling aggregates that were in those 100 L at that depth. After recovery, the MSC was left standing on deck for a few hours to allow the aggregates time to settle to the bottom part of the MSC. Hereafter, we gently drained the upper 95 L water from the MSC and removed the top part of the MSC, which left us with the bottom part of the MSC that now contained 5 L of seawater and all the settling aggregates from the 100 L of the sampled water column core. The bottom part of the MSC was brought to the laboratory where the aggregates were individually picked using a wide bore pipette and individually transferred to a vertical flow chamber (Ploug and Jrgensen, 1999). We measure the height, length, and depth of each aggregate in the flow chamber to determine its volume, equivalent spherical diameter, and shape. Hereafter, we adjusted an upward directed water flow in the flow chamber until it matched the downward settling velocity of the aggregate, allowing us to calculate the settling velocity of the aggregate from the flow rate in the system. While the aggregates were settling, we measured the oxygen concentration gradient at 50 μm steps from the surrounding water to the aggregate surface using an oxygen microsensor (OX-10, Unisense, Denmark) in the darkness and at *in situ* salinity and a temperature standard of 3.5°C . Using Fick's 2nd law of diffusion, we calculated the flux of oxygen ($\mu\text{mol O}_2 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) into the aggregate from the oxygen gradient according to Moradi et al. (2021) using the correction terms for spheres (Moradi et al., 2018). By multiplying the flux of oxygen into the aggregate by the total surface area of the aggregate (calculated for an ellipsoid for marine snow aggregates), we obtained the total microbial respiration rate within the aggregate ($\mu\text{mol O}_2 \text{ agg}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$). Using a respiratory quotient of 1 mol O_2 to 1 mol CO_2 , we calculate the total carbon respiration rate per aggregate ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ agg}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$), which we divided by the total carbon content of the aggregate ($\mu\text{mol POC agg}^{-1}$) to calculate the carbon-specific respiration rate (d^{-1}) of the aggregate, i.e. the amount of POC that is daily converted to CO_2 via microbial respiration (see Iversen and Ploug, 2010; Iversen et al., 2010; Iversen and Robert, 2015).

We microscopically determined the composition of all the aggregates that we measured in the flow chamber. We classified the individual

aggregates according to their composition, size, and type (fecal pellets, mucous aggregates, and aggregates containing cryogenic minerals), the aggregates were pooled and filtered on GF/F filter (Whatman, 25 mm) to determine dry weight, POC, and PON content (see *Biogeochemistry* section for methods).

2.7. Potential carbon-specific degradation from in situ camera profiles

In order to compare the microbial carbon-specific respiration rate to the overall attenuation processes through the water column, we estimated the potential carbon-specific degradation rate from the *in situ* camera profiles. This was done by determining the total POC concentration (POC_{conc} , $mgC\ m^{-3}$) of all the settling aggregates within a distinct depth-layer, i.e. at 15 m, 100 m and 200 m depth for the AW, the PW and the front:

$$POC_{conc} = \frac{F}{w_{av}}$$

where F represents the POC flux (F , $mgC\ m^{-2}\ d^{-1}$) and w_{av} the average sinking velocities of sinking aggregates (w_{av} , $m\ d^{-1}$).

The POC loss (POC_{loss} , $mgC\ m^{-3}\ d^{-1}$) was calculated as the negative quotient of the difference in POC flux and in depth (z , m) of 15 m to 100 m, 100 m to 200 m, and 200 m to 400 m, assuming vertical sinking of the organic material (Iversen, 2023):

$$POC_{loss} = -1 \frac{\Delta F}{\Delta z}$$

The potential carbon-specific degradation (C_{spec} , d^{-1}) was then calculated as the ratio between POC_{loss} and the POC_{conc} (Iversen, 2023):

$$C_{spec} = \frac{POC_{loss}}{POC_{conc}}$$

2.8. Statistical analyses

All statistical analyses and visualizations were done with the software R (RCoreTeam, 2019) and Python. To test the differences in sinking velocities between different aggregates types, the non-parametric Wilcoxon rank sum test was used. To compare the carbon-specific respiration rates according to the water masses (PW, AW, front), a Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test was used with a pairwise comparisons based on a Wilcoxon rank sum test as post-hoc test. To compare the aggregate size of the aggregates analyzed for carbon-specific respiration rates, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was done with a Tukey's multiple comparison test as post-hoc test. We used a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on the particle data observed with the camera system in the transect to identify the characteristics of the particles explaining the main variation.

3. Results

3.1. Water masses structure and biology

During the cruise, we observed several fronts on submesoscale (100 m – 1 km, hours to days) scales in the marginal ice zone (MIZ) (Hofmann et al., 2024). The resolution of our observation allowed to distinguish between individual (submesoscale) features of the larger mesoscale gradient (Hofmann et al., 2024). We categorized the features according to surface melt water, Polar Water (PW), Atlantic Water (AW), and the front - between colder, fresher water (melt water or PW) and warmer, saltier water (AW).

Along the camera transect, the (north-)westward moving warm and saline AW (3 - 5 °C, >34.5 PSU) was observed between 0 and 5 km distance and from 20 km onwards in the upper 100 m (Fig. 2 A, B, C and D). Very saline (>34.8) and warmer than 1.5 °C AW was distributed below 100 m throughout the transect. Colder and fresher PW

(temperature: 2 - 0 °C, salinity: 33.7 - 34.4) intruded from the north at 20 - 40 m depth between 5 and 12 km distance (Fig. 2 A, B, C and D). Between 0 and 10 km distance of the transect, meltwater with low salinities was located at the surface (temperature: 0.5 - 2 °C, salinity <33.3) between 0 and 15 m depth (Fig. 2 C and D). The Chla was distributed according to the water masses as detected from satellite data and vertical fluorescence profiles in the transect (Figs. 1 C and 2 E); the surface meltwater was low in Chla with <2 $mg\ m^{-3}$. High concentrations of Chla of >10 $mg\ m^{-3}$ were observed in the AW in the camera transect, with high values from the surface down to 40 m depth (Fig. 2 E).

Particle distributions were also consistent with water masses, showing patches of particles and aggregates over several meter depths with abundance peaks at around 35 to 65 m depth (Fig. 2 F). High particle and aggregate concentrations were observed below the high Chla concentration in the AW between 0 and 5 km distance and from 25 to 32 km, with the highest particle and aggregate concentrations and volumes located within the AW below the melt water at 0 - 5 km distance (Fig. 2 F and G). This occurred together with a ca. 1 m thin layer of elevated Chla concentrations (>12 $mg\ m^{-3}$), which was observed at the upper boundary of the AW, directly below the melt water.

The main differences in the morphological characteristics of the particles and aggregates were the size (equivalent spherical diameter, area, volume), the compactness (grey scale), and the circularity (PCA, Fig. S1 in the supplementary information). The average equivalent spherical diameter of the particles and aggregates was large below the chlorophyll-rich AW from 100 m to 200 m depth between 0 and 5 km distance and from 25 km onwards (Fig. 2 H). The circularity of the aggregates increased with increasing depth and was high below 100 m depth, while elongation was low (Fig. 2 I and J). Increased elongation was observed in the surface melt water only (Fig. 2 J). The mean grey level was lower below the chlorophyll-rich AW, suggesting an increased compactness of the particles (Fig. 2 K).

The distribution of copepods followed the depth of high chlorophyll, showing high and low concentrations in the AW and in the PW, respectively (Fig. 2 L). Other zooplankton, such as chaetognaths or ostracods, only occurred sporadically, showing no clear pattern in relation to water masses and depths (data not shown).

3.2. Nutrient and particle distribution for individual stations

The lowest nutrient concentrations were observed in the surface melt water (silicate: 2.2 - 3.3 μM , phosphate 0.1 - 0.4 μM , nitrate: 0.1 - 3.2 μM). In the PW, silicate concentrations were between 2.8 and 4.7 μM , phosphate concentrations between 0.4 and 0.6 μM , and nitrate concentrations between 4.2 and 10.3 μM . The AW had nutrient concentrations of 3.1 - 4.6 μM of silicate, 0.2 - 0.7 μM of phosphate, and 0.8 - 12.9 μM of nitrate. High ammonium concentrations were located between 20 m and 80 m, with maximum concentrations of 0.4 - 1.5 μM . From 100 m to 400 m, high silicate (4.6 - 5.6 μM), phosphate (0.6 - 0.8 μM), and nitrate (11.6 - 14.5 μM) concentrations were observed.

The particle and aggregate abundances at stations outside the transect (sampled 1 - 8 days after, 16 - 90 km away from the transect) showed either a single aggregate patch distributed over several meter depth, similar to the transect, or two separate shallower patches with peaks at depths of 25 - 50 m and 65 - 100 m (examples in Fig. 3). If two particle peaks were observed in the water column, higher Chla concentrations, i.e. from fluorescence data, were detected directly above the second particle peak (Fig. 3).

3.3. Carbon export

We categorized the different drifting traps as AW ($\approx 3 - 5$ °C), PW ($\approx -2 - 0$ °C) and a mixture at the front as shown in a temperature-salinity diagram, to compare biogeochemical fluxes (Fig. 4). The total mass flux was lowest in the PW (219 - 438 $mg\ m^{-2}\ d^{-1}$) and higher in

Fig. 2. (A) Cross-transverse flow velocities V_a and (B) along-transverse flow velocities U_a , (C) temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$], (D) salinity, (E) chlorophyll a from fluorescence sensor [mg m^{-3}], (F) total particle abundance [$\# \text{L}^{-1}$], (G) total particle volume [$\text{mm}^3 \text{L}^{-1}$], (H) average equivalent spherical diameter (ESD) [mm], (I) circularity, (J) elongation, (K) mean grey level, and (L) number of copepods [$\# \text{L}^{-1}$] in a camera transect (station 30 to 39) down to 400 m depth. The grey dotted lines show the position of the vertical profiles.

Fig. 3. Vertical profiles of aggregate abundance [$\# \text{L}^{-1}$] in grey and chlorophyll *a* (Chla) concentration [mg m^{-3}] in green according to depth [m] for station 50, 59, 70 and 99 showing peaks in aggregate concentration at depth with higher chlorophyll concentration located above.

the AW ($453 - 586 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and the front ($482 - 558 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, see biogeochemical fluxes in the supplementary information, Fig. S2). The overall contribution of the particulate organic carbon (POC) to the total mass flux was 9 – 17%. The highest POC fluxes were measured in the AW ($53 - 79 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and at the front ($49 - 62 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, Fig. 4 A).

The POC flux in the PW only amounted to $28 - 55 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$. The export efficiency of POC from the primary production in the surface to 100 m depth was between 13 and 22%, the transfer efficiency from 100 to 200 m depth between 60 and 86%, and from 200 m to 400 m between 85 and 99.5%, with the lowest efficiencies in the PW (Table 1). In the AW high biogenic silica (bSi) fluxes of $36 - 40 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ were observed (Fig. S2 in the supplementary information), but the average bSi concentration in all traps was below 10% of the total mass flux. The C:N ratio of the sinking material was between 11 and 15, with higher C:N ratio at depth in the PW and the front (Fig. S2 in the supplementary information).

3.4. Sinking velocities and respiration

The gel traps were deployed as part of the drifting trap array and

showed that the PW contained high abundances of small, settling crystalline minerals. This observation was supported by the MSC material collected in the PW, which also contained high abundances of crystalline minerals, both as single minerals and incorporated into settling organic aggregates. On board laboratory measurements of size and settling velocities showed that the aggregates containing crystalline minerals were fast sinking with velocities ranging between 36 and 1156 m d^{-1} (Fig. 5). The sinking velocities of aggregates without crystalline minerals in the PW, AW, and in the front were significantly lower ($3 - 144 \text{ m d}^{-1}$) than those measured for aggregates containing crystalline minerals (Wilcoxon rank sum test, p -value < 0.05 , Fig. 5). The carbon content of the aggregates containing minerals was below the limit of detection of the CN analyzer, indicating very low carbon content in the mineral-rich aggregates.

The carbon-specific respiration rate of the aggregates in the AW ($0.083 \pm 0.007 \text{ d}^{-1}$) was significantly higher (pairwise Wilcoxon rank sum test, p -value < 0.05) than in the PW ($0.017 \pm 0.013 \text{ d}^{-1}$) or the front ($0.010 \pm 0.004 \text{ d}^{-1}$). The aggregates measured for respiration were bigger in size (Tukey's multiple comparison test, p -value < 0.05) in the AW than in the PW and in the front, and higher in carbon content (Table 2).

Fig. 4. (A) Particulate organic carbon (POC) flux [$\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$] measured in the drifting sediment traps, and (B) the temperature-salinity diagram showing the Atlantic Water (purple, station 56), the front (turquoise, station 88), and the Polar Water (yellow, station 99). The dashed black lines show isopycnals.

Table 1

Primary production [$\text{mgC m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$], export efficiency to 100 m [%], transfer efficiency 100 m to 200 m [%] and 200 m to 400 m [%] in the Atlantic Water, the front, and the Polar Water. For comparison to other studies, we have calculated Martin's b for each POC flux profile as: $\text{Flux}_{400} = \text{Flux}_{100} (400/100)^b$ (see Giering et al., 2016).

	Primary production PP [$\text{mgC m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$]	Export efficiency PP to 100 m [%]	Transfer efficiency 100 m to 200 m [%]	Transfer efficiency 200 m to 400 m [%]	Martin's b
Atlantic Water	456	17	68	99.5	0.4
Front	278	22	86	92	0.07
Polar Water	421	13	60	85	0.41

Based on the POC loss measured using the primary production incubations and the drifting sediment traps, the calculated carbon-specific degradation rate between 15 m and 100 m was 5 to 28 times higher compared to the measured carbon-specific respiration rate and up to 9 times higher at depths between 100 m and 200 m (Fig. 6). At depths between 200 and 400 m, the calculated carbon-specific degradation rates from the front and the PW were similar to the directly measured rates, while the calculated rates were much lower than the measured rates for the AW.

3.5. Microscopic assessments

The plankton community consisted primarily of colonies of the haptophyte *Phaeocystis* and diatoms, including *Skeletonema*, *Chaetoceros*, *Fragilariopsis*, and *Pseudo-nitzschia*. Heterotrophic or mixotrophic degraders were associated with phytoplankton and aggregates, such as

Fig. 5. (A) Logarithmically scaled sinking velocities [m d^{-1}] according to logarithmically scaled equivalent spherical diameter [ESD, mm] of aggregates collected in the Atlantic Water, the Polar Water, and in the front, as well as settling velocities for PW aggregates containing minerals. (B) Sinking velocities [m d^{-1}] of aggregates without minerals and aggregates containing minerals. The horizontal line depicts the median, the box shows the 25th percentile and the 75th percentile, the whiskers represent a 1.5* interquartile range from the box and the points potential outliers.

Table 2

Sample size, average aggregate equivalent spherical diameter (ESD, mm), carbon specific respiration rate (d^{-1} , measured at 3.5 °C), settling velocity ($m s^{-1}$), and summed particulate organic carbon to dry weight ratio (POC:DW, %) for aggregates analyzed for respiration originating from the Atlantic Water, the front, and the Polar Water. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation.

	No. in sample [#]	Aggregate ESD [mm]	Carbon-specific respiration rate [d^{-1}]	Settling velocity [$m s^{-1}$]	Summed POC:DW [%]
Atlantic Water	4	1.8 \pm 0.3	0.083 \pm 0.007	52 \pm 21	47
Front	4	0.8 \pm 0.2	0.010 \pm 0.004	32 \pm 5	12
Polar Water	4	0.7 \pm 0.2	0.017 \pm 0.013	60 \pm 28	3

Fig. 6. Measured microbial respiration and calculated carbon-specific degradation [d^{-1}] in the Atlantic Water (purple, station 56), in the front (turquoise, station 88), and in the Polar Water (yellow, station 99) at 15 - 100 m, at 100 - 200 m, and at 200 - 400 m. The measured microbial carbon-specific respiration rate is based on direct measurements of aggregates collected by the Marine Snow Catcher, the calculated potential carbon-specific degradation is based on the loss of particulate organic carbon through the water column measured by the drift trap and primary production incubation, assuming vertical sinking of the organic matter. It is important to note that the direct measurements only include microbial degradation, while the estimates from the water column also include zooplankton grazing and disaggregation due to physical processes, in addition to microbial degradation.

ciliates, nanoflagellates and dinoflagellates, like *Protoperdinium* and *Gyrodinium*.

The marine snow aggregates were mostly formed from diatoms mixed with *Phaeocystis* that contained high mucous content. In the MSC and the drifting sediment traps, fecal pellets were only observed at low abundance, except for the traps that were deployed in the AW (Fig. S3 in the supplementary information). The majority of the aggregates were circular or semi-circular, compact and dense, with dark brownish coloring.

4. Discussion

4.1. Water mass structure and biology

In the front system, three different water masses interacted: Atlantic

Water (AW) transported by the West Spitsbergen Current, Polar Water (PW) carried by the East Greenland Current, and melt water derived from sea ice in the marginal ice zone (MIZ). The structure and mixing of these water masses determined the biogeochemical and biological processes in the front system in the MIZ. Although the study area had experienced low sea ice concentrations prior to our sampling, the remaining ice had retreated further north by the time of our study (data not shown). Melting sea ice produced a surface layer of cold (0 - 2 °C), low-salinity, nutrient-poor meltwater with low Chla concentrations that entered the study area from the northwest. At the surface, this meltwater encountered warmer, more saline AW (Fig. 1 C). At the resulting density front, the denser, Chla-rich AW was subducted beneath the meltwater to ~20 m depth. This subduction created a distinct Chla maximum within the AW immediately below the meltwater layer. Correspondingly, particle and aggregate abundances in the subducted AW were higher than in the non-subducted AW, resulting in increased total particle volume (Fig. 2F and G). The concentration of Chla at the upper boundary of the subducted AW likely enhanced encounter rates among small particles, such as phytoplankton cells, promoting aggregate formation (Jackson and Kjørboe, 2008). In general, the productive AW near the front exhibited higher Chla concentrations and higher aggregate abundances compared to the AW located further away from the frontal influence. These observations suggest that subduction at the meltwater-AW front both shoaled and concentrated phytoplankton biomass, stimulating the formation of large, compact aggregates compared with those found in meltwater, PW, or AW outside the frontal zone.

The high Chla and the associated increase in particle and aggregate abundance within the subducted AW directly influenced the zooplankton distribution in the frontal system. Copepod abundance closely followed the vertical patterns of Chla concentrations and particle and aggregate abundances (Fig. 2 L), consistent with the behavior of diel vertically migrating zooplankton, which ascend from depths and typically begin feeding from below the chlorophyll maximum, near the particle maximum (Jackson and Checkley Jr, 2011). This interpretation is further supported by elevated ammonium concentrations observed just below the Chla maximum. Because ammonium and urea are major excretion products of zooplankton (e.g. Conover and Gustavson, 1999; Hernández-León et al., 2008), these elevated concentrations indicate active zooplankton grazing at the lower boundary of the productive surface layer.

Zooplankton feeding activity seemed to directly impact the characteristics of sinking aggregates, likely via aggregate fragmentation (Dilling and Alldredge, 2000). Aggregate fragmentation has been shown to be responsible for half of the loss of large aggregates in the water column (Briggs et al., 2020). While aggregates were smaller in the surface layer, where copepods were more abundant (Fig. 2 L), the aggregate size increased below the depth of the aggregate abundance maximum at ~100 m (Fig. 2 H). This pattern suggests that rapidly sinking aggregates may have escaped copepod grazing and fragmentation at depths where zooplankton abundance was low (Fig. 2 L). Additionally, aggregates at depth became more circular and did not show increased elongation (Fig. 2I and J), indicating that copepod fecal pellets contributed only minimally to the total aggregate pool. This interpretation is supported by the gel trap samples from the frontal system, which contained fecal pellets only in low abundances.

Instead of fecal pellets, the downward flux was dominated by dense, circular phytoplankton aggregates with a characteristic brownish coloration. Several stations within the frontal system also showed high abundances of heterotrophic degraders, dinoflagellates, nanoflagellates, and ciliates, which are known to feed effectively on copepod fecal pellets (Hansen et al., 1996; Poulsen and Iversen, 2008; Poulsen et al., 2011). Hence, the low occurrence of fecal pellets may reflect intense grazing on the pellets by protozooplankton. Moreover, fragmentation of the fecal pellets by copepods themselves could decrease fecal pellet occurrence in the water column (Iversen and Poulsen, 2007). Hence, the export of fecal pellets at frontal system in the MIZ may be seasonal and determined by

the relative presence of fecal pellet producers and degraders (Svensen et al., 2019).

4.2. Carbon export

Although the flux of particulate organic carbon (POC) was lower in the PW than in the AW or at the front (Fig. 4), carbon export across all water masses in the frontal system was highly efficient. Between 13 and 22% of primary production was exported from the upper ocean to 100 m, 60 – 86% of that was transferred from 100 m to 200 m, and 85 – 99.5% was transferred from 200 m to 400 m. The higher carbon export efficiency and magnitude at front and AW suggest that the POC export in the Fram Strait may increase with further Atlantification and the continued inflow of AW (Polyakov et al., 2017; Randelhoff et al., 2018; Tesi et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2020). Strong boundary currents in the region promote horizontal advection, causing organic material at depth to originate from distant production areas (Weckerle et al., 2018). As a result, deep fluxes can exceed what would be expected from local surface primary production. Given the complex water movements in the frontal system, substantial lateral transport of sinking material is likely, creating a spatial decoupling between production and export, that must be considered when evaluating the efficiency of the biological carbon pump.

Based on the export and transfer efficiencies (Table 1), the highest biological activity and strongest attenuation occurred within the upper 200 m. The measured carbon-specific respiration rates were within the same range as previous observations in Polar and Atlantic Waters using similar methods (Belcher et al., 2016a, 2016b; van der Jagt et al., 2020), but they were still insufficient to explain the estimated *in situ* carbon-specific degradation rates within this layer (Fig. 6). Given the high copepod abundances in the upper 200 m (Fig. 2 L), zooplankton feeding likely accounted for most of the attenuation at these depths (Iversen et al., 2010; Jackson and Checkley Jr, 2011; Stemmann et al., 2004). Copepods are major grazers in the Arctic, and previous work has shown that *Calanus spp.* and *Pseudocalanus spp.* alone can explain more than 60% of total carbon attenuation (van der Jagt et al., 2020). Below 200 m, the observed attenuation can be largely explained by microbial respiration, indicating that zooplankton grazing on settling aggregates plays only a minor role at greater depths (Iversen et al., 2010; Stemmann et al., 2004).

4.3. Carbon specific respiration

The carbon-specific respiration rates were significantly higher in aggregates collected in AW than in PW or at the front (Table 2), even though all measurements were conducted at the same temperature (3.5 °C). Due to technical limitations of the experimental setup, aggregates from the colder PW (−1.7 °C) and the front (1.2 °C) were measured at temperatures above their *in situ* conditions. In principle, this temperature increase should elevate respiration rates (Iversen and Ploug, 2013), meaning that the true *in situ* carbon-specific respiration rates in aggregates formed in the PW and the front were likely even lower than our measured values. However, the aggregate-associated microbes had only minutes to adjust to the warmer incubation temperature, which could have caused a short-term temperature shock and led to an underestimation of respiration. In contrast, Iversen and Ploug (2013) allowed aggregates to acclimate for several days at constant temperatures before measuring microbial respiration. Additionally, we cannot rule out that differences in carbon or nutrient availability among water masses and within the aggregates altered the composition of aggregate-associated microbial communities, thereby affecting microbial degradation (Datta et al., 2016).

Given the higher carbon-specific respiration rates measured in AW (Table 2), one could expect a lower export efficiency in this water mass. Considering the temperature dependence of respiration, i.e. higher microbial activity at warmer temperature (Iversen and Ploug, 2013),

aggregates sinking through the warmer AW should, in principle, lose more carbon than those sinking through the colder PW, assuming similar sinking velocities and distances. However, this pattern was not observed, the lowest export and transfer efficiencies occurred in the PW (Table 1). It is important to note that applying our shipboard respiration measurements to deeper layers may lead to overestimations, because respiration of surface-derived aggregate-associated microbes generally declines with increasing hydrostatic pressure (Stief et al., 2021; Tamburini et al., 2013; Amano et al., 2022). Overall, our results indicate that the dominant carbon export mechanism, i.e. subduction and enhanced aggregate formation, exerts the stronger control on export efficiency and that the rate of microbial carbon-specific respiration is less important in the MIZ.

4.4. Export mechanism

In the frontal system, the subduction of Chla-rich water determines the depth of aggregate formation. In addition to enhanced aggregate formation just below the meltwater layer, deeper aggregate formation driven by subducted Chla-rich water may further increase carbon export. At several stations, a second peak in aggregate abundance was observed at 65 - 100 m depth, coinciding with elevated Chla concentration at depth (Fig. 3). Living phytoplankton can be transported into deeper water layers through eddy-driven subduction (Omand et al., 2015), frontal subduction (Hofmann et al., 2024), or alternating deep and shallow mixed layers (Dall'Olmo and Mork, 2014), enabling aggregation to occur well below the surface layer. Because salinity and temperature gradients retain aggregates in the surface ocean (Alldredge et al., 2002; MacIntyre et al., 1995; Möller et al., 2012; Seifert et al., 2019), meltwater-induced surface stratification limits the carbon export in the Arctic (von Appen et al., 2021). When aggregates form at greater depths, they form below the depths of strong stratification, are less retained by these gradients and, therefore, more likely to escape surface retention. Consequently, aggregate formation at depth, driven by subducted Chla-rich water, may enhance carbon export within the frontal system.

The dominant ballasting mechanism in the frontal system was the aggregate export via diatoms, i.e. silica ballasting. Most aggregates consisted of a mixture of diatoms and colonies of the haptophyte *Phaeocystis*. In Fram Strait, *Phaeocystis* abundances have been increasing, likely due to the warming and enhanced inflow of AW (Nöthig et al., 2015). We also observed high concentration of *Phaeocystis* colonies in the upper water layer of the frontal system. The polysaccharide-rich mucous matrix of *Phaeocystis* colonies makes them highly sticky and efficient at forming aggregates with diatoms (Alderkamp et al., 2007; Passow and Wassmann, 1994). This process facilitated the export of otherwise light and nearly neutrally buoyant *Phaeocystis* colonies (Peperzak et al., 2003), which rely on the heavy biogenic silica from diatom frustules for sinking (Tréguer et al., 2018). Because *Phaeocystis* colonies are carbon-rich and have high C/N ratios (Alderkamp et al., 2007), their incorporation into aggregates likely increased the particulate organic carbon content of the exported material and may explain the relatively high C/N ratios observed in our flux measurements (Fig. 2S in the supplementary information).

In PW, aggregate export was primarily driven by mineral ballasting. We observed a spontaneous export event in PW involving aggregates with incorporated crystalline structures, exhibiting high sinking velocities of up to 1156 m d^{−1} (Fig. 5). These minerals were likely cryogenic gypsum (Geilfus et al., 2013), which is abundant under Arctic sea ice (Wollenburg et al., 2018, 2020) and forms through precipitation in brine channels or pockets in sea ice during freezing (Geilfus et al., 2013; Wollenburg et al., 2020). Once the ice melts, the crystals are released from the ice, meaning that this process is most likely to occur during summer when the sea ice is melting. Gypsums crystals can sink at velocities between 200 and 7000 m d^{−1} (Wollenburg et al., 2020). When incorporated into aggregates, these fast-sinking minerals can transport

otherwise slow-sinking aggregates or suspended material downward, greatly increasing aggregate sinking velocity, similar to the effect of Saharan dust ballasting (van der Jagt et al., 2018). Consequently, aggregates formed from slow-sinking *Phaeocystis* with their sticky polysaccharide matrix can be efficiently exported when ballasted by cryogenic gypsum (Alderikamp et al., 2007; Passow and Wassmann, 1994; Swoboda et al., 2024; Wollenburg et al., 2018). However, these fast-sinking aggregates were low in carbon content, indicating limited carbon export. This likely explains why the PW exhibited lower export and transfer efficiencies (Table 1), despite the high abundance of crystalline particles captured in the gel traps.

4.5. Impact of frontal systems on carbon export in the Arctic

Eddies often develop near the ice edge and in areas with less than 20% ice cover (Kozlov and Atadzhanova, 2021), and with the overall decline in the extent of Arctic sea ice (Parkinson and DiGirolamo, 2021) we expect eddies to be more prominent in the future Arctic. Consequently, frontal systems are likely to become more frequent in the future. In areas with enhanced vertical and horizontal mixing, this could promote both carbon export and nutrient upwelling (Klein and Lapeyre, 2009; von Appen et al., 2018). Our results suggest that surface meltwater induced subduction of AW with high chlorophyll concentrations, leading to phytoplankton enrichment at depth, which enhanced aggregate formation. In particular, AW near the front appeared to drive high carbon export in the frontal system, despite high zooplankton grazing. This may help explain the observations by Fadeev et al. (2021a), who reported higher carbon export closer to the sea ice edge. However, differences in ecosystem states at the time of sampling could also contribute, as our study contained only residual ice and was dominated by meltwater at the surface. Large export events of ice-associated algae (Boetius et al., 2013) may therefore have occurred prior to our sampling.

We identified three main mechanisms that were driving carbon export in the frontal system; i) subduction of Chla-rich water promoted deep aggregate formation, allowing aggregates to escape the surface stratification and sink more rapidly, ii) most exported aggregates were composed of slow-sinking *Phaeocystis* colonies that were ballasted by diatoms, iii) some aggregates were ballasted by cryogenic minerals, which increased their size-specific settling velocities up to 10-fold compared to diatom-ballasted aggregates. Overall, our results suggest that the expansion of the MIZ, ongoing Atlantification, and the increasing frequency of frontal systems under climate change could substantially enhance carbon export in the future Arctic Ocean.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Lili Hufnagel: Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft. **Simon Ramondenc:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Christian Konrad:** Software, Methodology. **Wilken-Jon von Appen:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Zerlina Hofmann:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Sinhue Torres-Valdés:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jacqueline Stefels:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Nasrollah Moradi:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Astrid Bracher:** Data curation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Morten H. Iversen:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- Aagaard, K., Foldvik, A., Hillman, S., 1987. The West Spitsbergen current: disposition and water mass transformation. *J. Geophys. Res.*, Oceans 92 (C4), 3778–3784.
- Alderikamp, A.-C., Buma, A.G., van Rijssel, M., 2007. The carbohydrates of *Phaeocystis* and their degradation in the microbial food web. *Biogeochemistry* 83, 99–118.
- Allredge, A.L., Cowles, T.J., MacIntyre, S., Rines, J.E., Donaghay, P.L., Greenlaw, C.F., Holliday, D., Deksheniaks, M.M., Sullivan, J.M., Zaneveld, J.R.V., 2002. Occurrence and mechanisms of formation of a dramatic thin layer of marine snow in a shallow Pacific fjord. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 233, 1–12.
- Amano, C., Zhao, Z., Sintès, E., Reinthaler, T., Stefanschitz, J., Kisadur, M., Utsumi, M., Herndl, G.J., 2022. Limited carbon cycling due to high-pressure effects on the deep-sea microbiome. *Nat. Geosci.* 15 (12), 1041–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-022-01081-3>.
- Aminot, A., Kérouel, R., 2007. Dosage Automatique Des Nutriments Dans Les Eaux Marines: Méthodes En Flux Continu. Editions Quae.
- Aminot, A., Kérouel, R., Coverly, S.C., 2009. “Nutrients in Seawater Using Segmented Flow Analysis.” *Practical Guidelines for the Analysis of Seawater*, pp. 143–178.
- Arrigo, K.R., Perovich, D.K., Pickart, R.S., Brown, Z.W., Dijken, G.L.v., Lowry, K.E., Mills, M.M., Palmer, M.A., Balch, W.M., Bahr, F., Bates, N.R., Benitez-Nelson, C., Bowler, B., Brownlee, E., Ehn, J.K., Frey, K.E., Garley, R., Laney, S.R., Lubelczyk, L., Mathis, J., Matsuoka, A., Mitchell, B.G., Moore, G.W.K., Ortega-Retuerta, E., Pal, S., Polashenski, C.M., Reynolds, R.A., Schieber, B., Sosik, H.M., Stephens, M., Swift, J. H., 2012. Massive phytoplankton blooms under Arctic Sea ice. *Science* 336 (6087), 1408, 1408.
- Becker, S., Aoyama, M., Woodward, E.M.S., Bakker, K., Coverly, S., Mahaffey, C., Tanhua, T., 2020. GO-SHIP repeat hydrography nutrient manual: the precise and accurate determination of dissolved inorganic nutrients in seawater, using continuous flow analysis methods. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 7, 581790.
- Belcher, A., Iversen, M.H., Manno, C., Henson, S.A., Tarling, A.G., Sanders, R., 2016a. The role of particle associated microbes in remineralization of fecal pellets in the upper mesopelagic of the Scotia Sea, Antarctic. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 61 (3), 1049–1064.
- Belcher, A., Iversen, M.H., Giering, S., Riou, V., Henson, S.A., Berlin, L., Guilloux, L., Sanders, R., 2016b. Depth-resolved particle-associated microbial respiration in the northeast Atlantic. *Biogeosciences* 13, 4927–4943.
- Beszczynska-Möller, A., Fahrbach, E., Schauer, U., Hansen, E., 2012. Variability in Atlantic water temperature and transport at the entrance to the Arctic Ocean, 1997–2010. *ICES (Int. Counc. Explor. Sea) J. Mar. Sci.* 69 (5), 852–863.
- Bodungen, B.V., Wunsch, M., Fürderer, H., 1991. Sampling and analysis of suspended and sinking particles in the northern North Atlantic. In: Washington DC American Geophysical Union Geophysical Monograph Series, 63, pp. 47–56.
- Boetius, A., Albrecht, S., Bakker, K., Bienhold, C., Felden, J., Fernández-Méndez, M., Hendricks, S., Katlein, C., Lalande, C., Krumpfen, T., Nicolaus, M., Peeken, I.,

- Rabe, B., Rogacheva, A., Rybakova, E., Somavilla, R., Wenzhöfer, F., 2013. Export of algal biomass from the melting Arctic Sea ice. *Science* 339 (6126), 1430–1432.
- Boyd, P.W., Claustre, H., Levy, M., Siegel, D.A., Weber, T., 2019. Multi-faceted particle pumps drive carbon sequestration in the ocean. *Nature* 568 (7752), 327–335.
- Bracher, A., Xi, H., Dinter, T., Mangin, A., Strass, V., Von Appen, W.-J., Wiegmann, S., 2020. High resolution water column phytoplankton composition across the Atlantic Ocean from ship-towed vertical undulating radiometry. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 7, 235.
- Briggs, N., Dall'Olmo, G., Claustre, H., 2020. Major role of particle fragmentation in regulating biological sequestration of CO₂ by the oceans. *Science* 367 (6479), 791–793.
- Conover, R.J., Gustavson, K.R., 1999. Sources of urea in arctic seas: zooplankton metabolism. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 179, 41–54.
- Dall'Olmo, G., Mork, K.A., 2014. Carbon Export by Small Particles in the Norwegian Sea". *Climate Change and the Oceanic Carbon Cycle*. Apple Academic Press, pp. 131–146.
- Datta, M.S., Sliwerska, E., Gore, J., Polz, M.F., Cordero, O.X., 2016. Microbial interactions lead to rapid micro-scale successions on model marine particles. *Nat. Commun.* 7 (1), 11965.
- Dilling, L., Alldredge, A.L., 2000. Fragmentation of marine snow by swimming macrozooplankton: a new process impacting carbon cycling in the sea. *Deep Sea Res. Oceanogr. Res. Pap.* 47 (7), 1227–1245.
- England, M.R., Eisenman, I., Lutsko, N.J., Wagner, T.W., 2021. The recent emergence of Arctic amplification. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 48 e2021GL094086.
- Fadeev, E., Rogge, A., Ramondenc, S., Nöthig, E.-M., Wekerle, C., Bienhold, C., Salter, I., Waite, A.M., Hehemann, L., Boetius, A., 2021a. Sea ice presence is linked to higher carbon export and vertical microbial connectivity in the Eurasian Arctic Ocean. *Commun. Biol.* 4 (1), 1–13.
- Fadeev, E., Wietz, M., von Appen, W.J., Iversen, M.H., Nöthig, E.M., Engel, A., Grosse, J., Graeve, M., Boetius, A., 2021b. Submesoscale physicochemical dynamics directly shape bacterioplankton community structure in space and time. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 66 (7), 2901–2913.
- Geilfus, N.X., Galley, R., Cooper, M., Halden, N., Hare, A., Wang, F., Søgaard, D., Rysgaard, S., 2013. Gypsum crystals observed in experimental and natural sea ice. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 40 (24), 6362–6367.
- Giering, S.L.C., Sanders, R., Martin, A.P., Henson, S., Riley, J.S., Marsay, C.M., Johns, D. G., 2016. Particle flux in the oceans: challenging the steady state assumption. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* 31 (1), 159–171.
- Grasshoff, K., Kremling, K., Ehrhardt, M., 2009. *Methods of Seawater Analysis*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Hansen, B., Fotel, F.L., Jensen, N.J., Madsen, S.D., 1996. Bacteria associated with a marine planktonic copepod in culture. II. Degradation of fecal pellets produced on a diatom, a nanoflagellate or a dinoflagellate diet. *J. Plankton Res.* 18 (2), 275–288.
- Hattermann, T., Isachsen, P.E., von Appen, W.J., Albrechtsen, J., Sundfjord, A., 2016. Eddy-driven recirculation of Atlantic water in Fram Strait. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 43 (7), 3406–3414.
- Hernández-León, S., Fraga, C., Ikeda, T., 2008. A global estimation of mesozooplankton ammonium excretion in the open ocean. *Plankton Res.* 30 (5), 577–585. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbn021>.
- Håvik, L., Pickart, R., Våge, K., Torres, D., Thurnherr, A., Beszczynska-Möller, A., Walczowski, W., von Appen, W.J., 2017. Evolution of the East Greenland current from Fram Strait to Denmark Strait: synoptic measurements from summer 2012. *J. Geophys. Res., Oceans* 122 (3), 1974–1994.
- Hofmann, Z., von Appen, W.-J., Wekerle, C., 2021. Seasonal and mesoscale variability of the two Atlantic water recirculation pathways in Fram Strait. *J. Geophys. Res., Oceans* 126 (7) e2020JC017057.
- Hofmann, Z., von Appen, W.-J., Kanzow, T., Becker, H., Hagemann, J., Hufnagel, L., Iversen, M.H., 2024. Stepwise subduction observed at a front in the marginal ice zone in Fram Strait. *J. Geophys. Res., Oceans* 129 (5) e2023JC020641.
- Holmes, R.M., Aminot, A., Kérouel, R., Hooker, B.A., Peterson, B.J., 1999. A simple and precise method for measuring ammonium in marine and freshwater ecosystems. *Can. J. Fish. Aquat. Sci.* 56 (10), 1801–1808.
- Hu, C., Lee, Z., Franz, B., 2012. Chlorophyll algorithms for oligotrophic oceans: a novel approach based on three-band reflectance difference. *J. Geophys. Res., Oceans* 117 (C1).
- Hydes, D., Aoyama, M., Aminot, A., Bakker, K., Becker, S., Coverly, S., Daniel, A., Dickson, A., Grosso, O., Kerouel, R., 2010. Recommendations for the Determination of Nutrients in Seawater to High Levels of Precision and Inter-comparability Using Continuous Flow Analysers. GO-SHIP (Unesco/IOC).
- Iversen, M.H., 2023. Carbon export in the ocean: a biologist's perspective. *Ann. Rev. Mar. Sci.* 15, 357–381.
- Iversen, M.H., Nowald, N., Ploug, H., Jackson, G.A., Fischer, G., 2010. High resolution profiles of vertical particulate organic matter export off Cape Blanc, Mauritania: degradation processes and ballasting effects. *Deep Sea Res. Oceanogr. Res. Pap.* 57 (6), 771–784.
- Iversen, M.H., Ploug, H., 2010. Ballast minerals and the sinking carbon flux in the ocean: carbon-specific respiration rates and sinking velocity of marine snow aggregates. *Biogeosciences* 7, 2613–2624.
- Iversen, M.H., Ploug, H., 2013. Temperature effects on carbon-specific respiration rate and sinking velocity of diatom aggregates—potential implications for deep ocean export processes. *Biogeosciences* 10 (6), 4073–4085.
- Iversen, M.H., Poulsen, L.K., 2007. Coprophagy, coprophagy, and coprochaly in the copepods *Calanus helgolandicus*, *Pseudocalanus elongatus*, and *Oithona similis*. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 350, 79–89.
- Iversen, M.H., Robert, M.L., 2015. Ballasting effects of smectite on aggregate formation and export from a natural plankton community. *Mar. Chem.* 175, 18–27.
- Jackson, G.A., Checkley Jr, D.M., 2011. Particle size distributions in the upper 100 m water column and their implications for animal feeding in the plankton. *Deep Sea Res. Oceanogr. Res. Pap.* 58 (3), 283–297.
- Jackson, G.A., Kiorboe, T., 2008. Maximum phytoplankton concentrations in the sea. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 53 (1), 395–399.
- Kirkwood, D., 1996. *Nutrients: Practical Notes on their Determination in Sea Water*. Klein, P., Lapeyre, G., 2009. The oceanic vertical pump induced by mesoscale and submesoscale turbulence. *Ann. Rev. Mar. Sci.* 1, 351–375.
- Kozlov, I.E., Atadzhanova, O.A., 2021. Eddies in the marginal ice zone of Fram Strait and Svalbard from spaceborne SAR observations in winter. *Remote Sens.* 14 (1), 134.
- MacIntyre, S., Alldredge, A.L., Gotschalk, C.C., 1995. Accumulation of marines now at density discontinuities in the water column. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 40 (3), 449–468.
- Mahadevan, A., 2016. The impact of submesoscale physics on primary productivity of plankton. *Ann. Rev. Mar. Sci.* 8, 161–184.
- Möller, K.O., John, M.S., Temming, A., Floeter, J., Sell, A.F., Herrmann, J.-P., Möllmann, C., 2012. Marine snow, zooplankton and thin layers: indications of a trophic link from small-scale sampling with the video Plankton recorder. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 468, 57–69.
- Moradi, N., Klawonn, I., Iversen, M.H., Wenzhöfer, F., Grossart, H.-P., Ploug, H., Fischer, G., Khalili, A., 2021. A novel measurement-based model for calculating diffusive fluxes across substrate-water interfaces of marine aggregates, sediments and biofilms. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 8, 689977.
- Moradi, N., Liu, B., Iversen, M., Kuypers, M.M., Ploug, H., Khalili, A., 2018. A new mathematical model to explore microbial processes and their constraints in phytoplankton colonies and sinking marine aggregates. *Sci. Adv.* 4 (10) eaat1991.
- Neukermans, G., Oziel, L., Babin, M., 2018. Increased intrusion of warming Atlantic water leads to rapid expansion of temperate phytoplankton in the Arctic. *Glob. Change Biol.* 24 (6), 2545–2553.
- Nöthig, E.-M., Bracher, A., Engel, A., Metfies, K., Niehoff, B., Peeken, I., Bauerfeind, E., Cherkasheva, A., Gäbler-Schwarz, S., Harge, K., 2015. Summer time plankton ecology in Fram Strait—A compilation of long-and short-term observations. *Polar Res.* 34 (1), 23349.
- Omand, M.M., D'Asaro, E.A., Lee, C.M., Perry, M.J., Briggs, N., Cetinić, I., Mahadevan, A., 2015. Eddy-driven subduction exports particulate organic carbon from the spring bloom. *Science* 348 (6231), 222–225.
- Parkinson, C.L., DiGirolamo, N.E., 2021. Sea ice extents continue to set new records: arctic, Antarctic, and global results. *Rem. Sens. Environ.* 267, 112753.
- Passow, U., Wassmann, P., 1994. On the trophic fate of *Phaeocystis pouchetii* (Hariot): IV. The formation of marine snow by *P. pouchetii*. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 153–161.
- Peperzak, L., Colijn, F., Koeman, R., Gieskes, W., Joordens, J., 2003. Phytoplankton sinking rates in the Rhine region of freshwater influence. *J. Plankton Res.* 25 (4), 365–383.
- Picheral, M., Colin, S., Irisson, J.-O., 2017. *Ecotaxa, a Tool for the Taxonomic Classification of Images*. City.
- Picheral, M., Guidi, L., Stemann, L., Karl, D.M., Iddaoud, G., Gorsky, G., 2010. The Underwater vision profiler 5: an advanced instrument for high spatial resolution studies of particle size spectra and zooplankton. *Limnol. Oceanogr. Methods* 8 (9), 462–473.
- Ploug, H., Jørgensen, B.B., 1999. A net-jet flow system for mass transfer and microsensor studies of sinking aggregates. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 176, 279–290.
- Polyakov, I.V., Pnyushkov, A.V., Alkire, M.B., Ashik, I.M., Baumann, T.M., Carmack, E. C., Goszczko, I., Guthrie, J., Ivanov, V.V., Kanzow, T., 2017. Greater role for Atlantic inflows on sea-ice loss in the Eurasian Basin of the Arctic Ocean. *Science* 356 (6335), 285–291.
- Poulsen, L.K., Iversen, M.H., 2008. Degradation of copepod fecal pellets: key role of protozooplankton. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 367, 1–13.
- Poulsen, L.K., Moldrup, M., Berge, T., Hansen, P.J., 2011. Feeding on copepod fecal pellets: a new trophic role of dinoflagellates as detritivores. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 441, 65–78.
- Ramondenc, S., Eveillard, D., Metfies, K., Iversen, M.H., Nöthig, E.-M., Piepenburg, D., Hasemann, C., Soltwedel, T., 2025. Unveiling pelagic-benthic coupling associated with the biological carbon pump in the Fram Strait (Arctic Ocean). *Nat. Commun.* 16, 840.
- Ramondenc, S., Nöthig, E.M., Hufnagel, L., Bauerfeind, E., Busch, K., Knüppel, N., Kraft, A., Schröter, F., Seifert, M., Iversen, M.H., 2023. Effects of Atlantification and changing sea-ice dynamics on zooplankton community structure and carbon flux between 2000 and 2016 in the eastern Fram Strait. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 68, S39–S53.
- Randelhoff, A., Reigstad, M., Chierici, M., Sundfjord, A., Ivanov, V., Cape, M., Vernet, M., Tremblay, J.-É., Bratbak, G., Kristiansen, S., 2018. Seasonality of the physical and biogeochemical hydrography in the inflow to the Arctic Ocean through Fram Strait. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 5, 224.
- Rantanen, M., Karpechko, A.Y., Lipponen, A., Nordling, K., Hyvärinen, O., Ruosteenoja, K., Wihma, T., Laaksonen, A., 2022. The Arctic has warmed nearly four times faster than the globe since 1979. *Commun. Earth Environ.* 3, 168.
- RCoreTeam, 2019. *R: a Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for statistical computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Reigstad, M., Wassmann, P., 2007. Does *Phaeocystis* spp. contribute significantly to vertical export of organic carbon? *Phaeocystis* 217–234 major link in the biogeochemical cycling of climate-relevant elements.
- Rogge, A., Janout, M., Loginova, N., Trudnowska, E., Hörstmann, C., Wekerle, C., Oziel, L., Schourup-Kristensen, V., Ruiz-Castille, E., Schulz, K., Povazhny, V.V., Iversen, M.H., Waite, A.M., 2022. Carbon dioxide sink in the Arctic Ocean from cross-shelf transport of dense Barent Sea water. *Nat. Geosci.* 16, 82–88.
- Seifert, M., Hoppema, M., Burau, C., Friedrichs, A., Geuer, J.K., John, U., Koch, B.P., Konrad, C., van der Jagt, H., Iversen, M.H., 2019. Influence of glacial meltwater on

- summer biogeochemical cycles in Scoresby Sund, East Greenland. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 13 (6).
- Serreze, M.C., Francis, J.A., 2006. The Arctic Amplification debate. *Clim. Change* 76, 241–264.
- Stefels, J., Dacey, J.W., Elzenga, J.T.M., 2009. In vivo DMSP-biosynthesis measurements using stable-isotope incorporation and proton-transfer-reaction mass spectrometry (PTR-MS). *Limnol Oceanogr. Methods* 7 (8), 595–611.
- Stemmann, L., Jackson, G.A., Gorsky, G., 2004. A vertical model of particle size distributions and fluxes in the midwater column that includes biological and physical processes—Part II: application to a three year survey in the NW Mediterranean Sea. *Deep Sea Res. Oceanogr. Res. Pap.* 51 (7), 885–908.
- Stief, P., Elvert, M., Glud, R.N., 2021. Respiration by "marine snow" at high hydrostatic pressure: insights from continuous oxygen measurements in a rotating pressure tank. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 66 (7), 2797–2809.
- Strong, C., Rigor, I.G., 2013. Arctic marginal ice zone trending wider in summer and narrower in winter. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 40 (18), 4864–4868.
- Svensen, C., Halvorsen, E., Vernet, M., Franze, G., Dmoch, K., Lavrentyev, P.J., Kwasiński, S., 2019. Zooplankton communities associated with new and regenerated primary production in the Atlantic inflow north of Svalbard. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 6, 293.
- Swoboda, S., Krumpen, T., Nöthig, E.-M., Metfies, K., Ramondenc, S., Wollenburg, J., Fahl, K., Peeken, I., Iversen, M.H., 2024. Release of ballast material during sea-ice melt enhances carbon export in the Arctic Ocean. *PNAS Nexus* 3 (4) gae081.
- Tamburini, C., Boutrif, M., Garel, M., Colwell, R.R., Deming, J.W., 2013. Prokaryotic responses to hydrostatic pressure in the ocean - a review. *Environ. Microbiol.* 15 (5), 1262–1274.
- Tesi, T., Muschitiello, F., Mollenhauer, G., Miserocchi, S., Langone, L., Ceccarelli, C., Panieri, G., Chiggiato, J., Nogarotto, A., Hefter, J., 2021. Rapid atlantification along the Fram Strait at the beginning of the 20th century. *Sci. Adv.* 7 (48) eabj2946.
- Tippenhauer, S., Janout, M., Chouksey, M., Torres-Valdes, S., Fong, A., Wulff, T., 2021. Substantial sub-surface chlorophyll patch sustained by vertical nutrient fluxes in Fram Strait observed with an autonomous underwater vehicle. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 8, 605225.
- Tréguer, P., Bowler, C., Moriceau, B., Dutkiewicz, S., Gehlen, M., Aumont, O., Bittner, L., Dugdale, R., Finkel, Z., Iudicone, D., 2018. Influence of diatom diversity on the ocean biological carbon pump. *Nat. Geosci.* 11 (1), 27–37.
- Trudnowska, E., Lacour, L., Ardyna, M., Rogge, A., Irisson, J.O., Waite, A.M., Babin, M., Stemmann, L., 2021. Marine snow morphology illuminates the evolution of phytoplankton blooms and determines their subsequent vertical export. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 2816. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-22994-4>.
- van der Jagt, H., Friese, C., Stuut, J.B.W., Fischer, G., Iversen, M.H., 2018. The ballasting effect of Saharan dust deposition on aggregate dynamics and carbon export: aggregation, settling, and scavenging potential of marine snow. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 63 (3), 1386–1394.
- van der Jagt, H., Wiedmann, I., Hildebrandt, N., Niehoff, B., Iversen, M.H., 2020. Aggregate feeding by the copepods *Calanus* and *Pseudocalanus* controls carbon flux attenuation in the Arctic shelf sea during the productive period. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 7.
- von Appen, W.-J., Waite, A.M., Bergmann, M., Bienhold, C., Boebel, O., Bracher, A., Cisewski, B., Hagemann, J., Hoppema, M., Iversen, M.H., 2021. Sea-ice derived meltwater stratification slows the biological carbon pump: results from continuous observations. *Nat. Commun.* 12 (1), 7309.
- von Appen, W.J., Wekerle, C., Hehemann, L., Schourup-Kristensen, V., Konrad, C., Iversen, M.H., 2018. Observations of a submesoscale cyclonic filament in the marginal ice zone. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 45 (12), 6141–6149.
- Wang, Q., Wekerle, C., Wang, X., Danilov, S., Koldunov, N., Sein, D., Sidorenko, D., von Appen, W.J., Jung, T., 2020. Intensification of the Atlantic water supply to the Arctic Ocean through Fram Strait induced by Arctic sea ice decline. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 47 (3) e2019GL086682.
- Wekerle, C., Krumpen, T., Dinter, T., von Appen, W.-J., Iversen, M.H., Salter, I., 2018. Properties of sediment trap catchment areas in Fram Strait: results from lagrangian modeling and remote sensing. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 5.
- Wollenburg, J.E., Iversen, M., Katlein, C., Krumpen, T., Nicolaus, M., Castellani, G., Peeken, I., Flores, H., 2020. New observations of the distribution, morphology and dissolution dynamics of cryogenic gypsum in the Arctic Ocean. *Cryosphere* 14 (6), 1795–1808.
- Wollenburg, J.E., Katlein, C., Nehrke, G., Nöthig, E.M., Matthiessen, J., Wolf-Gladrow, D.A., Nikolopoulos, A., Gázquez-Sánchez, F., Rossmann, L., Assmy, P., Babin, M., Bruyant, F., Beaulieu, M., Dybwad, C., Peeken, I., 2018. Ballasting by cryogenic gypsum enhances carbon export in a *Phaeocystis* under-ice bloom. *Sci. Rep.* 8 (1), 7703.